

Judul: Accepted Letter

Tanggal: 2020-08-30 07:38

Pengirim: "Joana Katina" <joana@getweb.lt>

Penerima: "Mr Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Dear Dr Achmad Faqih

The editing of your submission, "Regressing Climate Change, Agricultural Growth And Food Production On Economic Sustainability: Gathering And Analyzing Data For Asean Countries" is complete. We are now sending it to review.

Sincerely,

Thanks

Publication Team

<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/>

Judul: Review

Tanggal: 2020-09-28 07:14

Pengirim: "Joana Katina" <joana@getweb.lt>

Penerima: "Mr Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

This is to inform you that Editorial office of Journal of Security and Sustainability Issue, has received peer reviews comments/suggestions for the following articles

You are expected to revise your manuscript as per the following suggestions. Read all part of the email carefully and act without fail.

Reviewer A comments:

Please do revise your manuscript as per suggestion inside the manuscript.

Further comments are indicated inside the file. See them and revise accordingly. After corrections kindly indicate at the same place that the corrections are done by writing [Done] in square brackets.

Reviewer B comments:

- The manuscript must be arranged as per **attached JSSI template**. Especially abstract should be written in 5 subheadings of Purpose, Methodology, Main findings, Implications, Novelty.
- The title should tell the true story of the research article.
- First two lines of the abstract should tell about what has been done in this research. Don't tell the background of research in the abstract. All background information should go in the introduction section.
- Enter six (6) keywords that truly represent the essence of research work. Three keywords should be in article title also.

Note on Plagiarism and Similarity:

JSSI Journals follows ZERO Plagiarism policy. We check all articles by iThenticate (Turnitin software). You are expected to see attached similarity report as well and take the following actions:

1. Wherever you see the similarity, full paragraph or 2 to 3 lines full copy-pasted, you need to rewrite in your words. It will reduce similarity.
2. If you are taking any text, information, idea, images, data, table, etc. from some source then you should do paraphrasing and you have to give citations to that source. Otherwise, the article will be labeled as Plagiarized and Rejected and no query will be entertained.
3. If your Similarity index is above 10%. You need to send a new Turnitin report from your side showing a similarity of less than 10%.

NB.

Note: Kindly **do all revisions in an attached file only, don't change file name or extension** and send me back within 3 days. If you are not following the above suggestions, either your article will be rejected or delayed.

Judul: Accepted Letter
Tanggal: 2020-10-30 04:32
Pengirim: "Joana Katina" <joana@getweb.lt>
Penerima: "Mr Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Dear Author,

Greetings from the Editorial Team of Journal of Security and Sustainability Issue!
Thank you very much for presenting your paper for the evaluation of Journal of Security and Sustainability Editorial Team.

We would like to inform you that your paper titled "Regressing Climate Change, Agricultural Growth And Food Production On Economic Sustainability: Gathering And Analyzing Data For Asean Countries" was accepted by Journal of Security and Sustainability but due to delay from your side, your paper/article is still due for publishing. Respective notification letter of related paper has been already sent to you.

Reference Number : JSSI-0420-33586

***Important:**

Please ensure to complete all the above mentioned next steps by 31 Oct 2020 to ensure timely publication of the mentioned papers.

Note: Please ignore this mail if you have already completed the registration process. We'll send you the confirmation email soon if you have not yet received the acknowledgement regarding your registration.

Thanks
Publication Team
<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/>

Journal Of Security And Sustainability Issues

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ACCEPTANCE LETTER TO AUTHOR

Dear Author,

With reference to your paper submitted "[Regressing Climate Change, Agricultural Growth And Food Production On Economic Sustainability: Gathering And Analyzing Data For Asean Countries](#)" we are pleased to accept the same for publication in JSSI, **Volume X, OCTOBER 2020**.

Manuscript ID: JSSI/1946

The Fee includes:

Online maintenance and processing charge.

Certificate & Hard Copy of Journal Paper.

No limitation of number of pages.

Editorial fee.

Taxes.

Sincerely,
Best regards,
Thanks
Publication Team
<https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/>